

THE ROLE OF FORMATIVE EVALUATION IN DEVELOPING SOCIOCULTURAL COMPETENCE IN MIDDLE SCHOOL LEARNERS

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***Abstract.** This article studies sociocultural competence development with the help of evaluation in foreign language teaching to middle school learners. It also describes the importance of formative assessment and promoting sociocultural competence in middle school learners' education, emphasizing the role of educators in integrating multicultural content, fostering collaborative activities, and employing formative assessment strategies. Apart from that this research addresses the challenges of integrating sociocultural competence into foreign language teaching in middle school classes.*

***Keywords.** sociocultural competence, foreign language teaching, multicultural content, formative assessment, middle school learners, multicultural community, cultural difference, self-assessment, feedback.*

Nowadays in the field of foreign language education, sociocultural competence is becoming an increasingly significant way of effective teaching, especially for middle school learners. Sociocultural competence involves the ability to navigate cultural differences, understand diverse perspectives of people, and communicate effectively in cross-cultural contexts. Intentional learning refers to cognitive processes that have learning as a goal rather than an incidental outcome (Bereiter & Scardamalia, 1989). Middle school students are in a critical phase of cognitive, social, and emotional development, and these skills help them to engage with an increasingly interconnected world by learning foreign languages. The cultivation of sociocultural development in middle school education paves the way to be

successful and competitive in today's globalized world, and to make effective communication in multicultural communities.

Foreign language teaching in middle school classes inherently lends itself to the development of sociocultural competence. The language learning process is connected with culture, and learning a new language gives students many insights into the values, traditions, customs, and social norms of the communities where the language is spoken. With the help of the integration of cultural content into language lessons, educators can make language learning more interesting and engaging and learners might be more taught effectively. For example, teaching idiomatic expressions, holidays, or historical stories helps students see the language as a booster of comprehension of diverse cultural roots.

The role of formative assessment in thriving sociocultural competence in foreign language education is more important to middle school learners. Formative assessment changes the focus from only learning grammar and vocabulary to understanding and applying language in cultural contexts. By organizing role-plays, debates, and cultural discussion projects, students can actively learn a foreign language. For instance, a formative task might include students researching and presenting on traditional customs of a target language's culture, followed by a peer review session where students discuss their findings.

Moreover, formative assessment provides teachers with continuous feedback about learners, allowing students to reflect on their progress in both linguistic and cultural competencies. It means formative assessment is the key feature in the development of sociocultural competence in teaching middle school learners. Self-assessment and peer feedback tasks can encourage learners to assess their cultural comprehension, enhancing their ability to navigate intercultural situations. In addition, formative assessment is very crucial in the developmental needs of middle school learners.

The difficulties in the process of integrating sociocultural competence into foreign language teaching should be paid attention. Teachers may come across

challenges such as insufficient training in cultural instruction, lack of resources and materials, or time limitations within the schedule. These barriers require professionally approached development of classroom management and access to authentic and creative materials based on cultural contexts, such as movies, music, and literature from the target language's culture.

In conclusion, developing sociocultural competence through foreign language teaching in middle school is crucial in the preparation of learners to thrive in a multicultural, globalized, and fast-paced world. Relationship between language instruction and sociocultural education and the use of formative assessment strategies, foreign language teachers can create extraordinary, energetic, culturally aware, and linguistically proficient individuals. Teachers can build meaningful connections across cultures and teach how to compare the traditions and cultural heritage of different countries, and it helps every middle school learner to possess their own interpersonal skills soon.

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